

Evaluating the Body Mass Index, Blood Glucose and Serum Insulin Levels in Adolescents Acne

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Abstract:

Background: Acne vulgaris is a prevalent dermatological condition among adolescents, with multifactorial etiology including hormonal, genetic, and lifestyle factors. Emerging evidence suggests a potential link between metabolic health and acne severity. This study aims to evaluate the associations between body mass index (BMI), blood glucose, and serum insulin levels in adolescents with acne.

Methods: A total of 180 adolescents with acne were included. Demographic data, BMI, fasting blood glucose, and serum insulin levels were collected. Acne severity was categorized into mild, moderate, and severe groups. Statistical analyses, including ANOVA, Pearson correlation, and multiple linear regression, were performed using SPSS version 23.0.

Results: Participants had a mean age of 15.6 years, with a balanced gender distribution. Significant differences in BMI ($p < 0.001$), fasting blood glucose ($p = 0.003$), and serum insulin levels ($p < 0.001$) were observed across acne severity groups. Higher BMI, blood glucose, and insulin levels were associated with more severe acne. Correlation analysis revealed positive correlations between BMI and serum insulin ($r = 0.42$), BMI and blood glucose ($r = 0.27$), and serum insulin and blood glucose ($r = 0.34$). Regression analysis identified BMI, blood glucose, and serum insulin as significant predictors of acne severity ($p < 0.001$).

Conclusion: The study highlights significant associations between metabolic health and acne severity in adolescents. Higher BMI, blood glucose, and serum insulin levels correlate with more severe acne, suggesting that metabolic dysfunctions play a role in acne pathogenesis.

Recommendations: Addressing metabolic health, alongside traditional dermatological treatments, may enhance acne management. Further research is needed to explore underlying mechanisms and develop integrated treatment approaches.

Keywords: Acne Vulgaris, Adolescents, Body Mass Index, Blood Glucose, Serum Insulin.

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Introduction

One of the most prevalent dermatological disorders affecting teenagers globally is acne vulgaris, which can have serious effects on both physical and mental health. Comedones, papules, pustules, and, in more severe cases, cysts and nodules are the hallmarks of this condition, which primarily affects the face, neck, chest, and back. Although a variety of factors, including increased sebum production, follicular hyperkeratinization, bacterial colonisation (mainly *Cutibacterium* acnes), and inflammation, contribute to the pathophysiology of acne, recent studies have started to emphasise the possible

significance of metabolic factors in the onset and severity of acne [1].

Significant hormonal changes that might affect skin condition and metabolic health occur during adolescence. Acne aetiology has been linked to insulin resistance, a disease often associated with obesity and polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS). As a consequence of increased testosterone production brought on by insulin resistance, hyperinsulinemia can worsen acne by promoting keratinocyte proliferation and sebaceous gland activity [2]. Moreover, a number of studies have linked a higher incidence of acne to high glycaemic

load meals, which are known to raise insulin and blood glucose levels.

There has also been a lot of interest in the connection between body mass index (BMI) and acne. Higher levels of oxidative stress and inflammatory cytokines are frequently associated with obesity and overweight situations, both of which can influence the aetiology of acne. Furthermore, adipose tissue secretes a range of hormones and inflammatory mediators that can affect the condition of the skin, acting as an endocrine organ [3]. Research indicates that teenagers with greater body mass index (BMI) had a higher likelihood of having severe forms of acne, indicating a possible correlation between acne severity and metabolic health [4].

Despite these associations, the precise mechanisms through which metabolic factors influence acne remain unclear. Recent advances in understanding the metabolic underpinnings of acne have opened new avenues for research and treatment strategies. By elucidating the links between BMI, blood glucose, and serum insulin levels with acne severity, healthcare providers can develop more targeted and effective treatment protocols that address both dermatological and metabolic aspects of the condition.

This study aims to evaluate the body mass index (BMI), blood glucose, and serum insulin levels in adolescents with acne.

Methodology

Study Design: A cross-sectional observational study.

Study Setting: The study took place during a period of March 2017 - February 2018 at Dermatology Department, NMCH, Patna, Bihar, India.

Participants: A total of 180 adolescents with acne participated in the study.

Inclusion Criteria

- Adolescents aged 12-18 years.
- Diagnosed with acne by a dermatologist.

Exclusion Criteria

- Adolescents with a history of diabetes or other endocrine disorders.
- Use of systemic or topical acne treatments within the past 3 months.
- Any chronic illness or medication that could affect insulin levels.

- Pregnant or lactating females.

Bias: To minimize selection bias, participants were randomly selected from the dermatology outpatient department. Information bias was reduced by training data collectors and using standardized procedures for all measurements.

Data Collection

Data were collected through:

- Structured questionnaires to gather demographic information and medical history.
- Clinical examination to assess acne severity.
- Measurements of height and weight to calculate BMI.
- Blood samples to determine fasting blood glucose and serum insulin levels.

Procedure: Adolescents visiting the dermatology department and meeting the inclusion criteria were invited to participate in the study. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants and their guardians. Participants completed a structured questionnaire regarding their demographics and medical history. A dermatologist assessed the severity of acne using standardized grading scales.

To compute BMI (kg/m²), height and weight were measured with a stadiometer and a digital scale, respectively. Serum insulin and blood glucose levels were measured in the morning after fasting blood samples were taken. Hexokinase was used to test blood glucose, and an enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) was used to evaluate serum insulin.

Statistical Analysis: SPSS version 23.0 was used to analyse the data. The demographic and clinical features of the subjects were summed together using descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation). The associations between serum insulin levels, blood glucose, and BMI were investigated using regression analysis and Pearson correlation. P-values less than 0.05 were deemed statistically significant.

Result

The study included 180 teenage participants with acne. The participants' mean age was 15.6 years (SD = 1.8), with 88 (48.9%) males and 92 (51.1%) females. The average fasting blood glucose level was 89.6 mg/dL (SD = 10.4), the average BMI was 23.4 kg/m² (SD = 4.2), and the average serum insulin level was 12.5 µIU/mL (SD = 4.8).

Table 1: Demographic and Clinical Characteristics

Characteristic	Value
Age (years)	15.6 ± 1.8
Gender	
- Female	92 (51.1%)
- Male	88 (48.9%)
BMI (kg/m ²)	23.4 ± 4.2
Fasting Blood Glucose (mg/dL)	89.6 ± 10.4
Serum Insulin (μIU/mL)	12.5 ± 4.8

Participants were categorized into three acne severity groups: mild (n=72), moderate (n=76), and severe (n=32). The mean BMI for each group was 21.8 kg/m² (SD = 3.8) for mild acne, 23.6 kg/m² (SD = 4.0) for moderate acne, and 26.0 kg/m² (SD = 4.5) for severe acne. ANOVA analysis showed a significant difference in BMI across the acne severity groups (F(2, 177) = 8.45, p < 0.001).

Table 2: BMI Across Acne Severity Groups

Acne Severity	Mean BMI (kg/m ²)	N	p-value
Mild	21.8 ± 3.8	72	<0.001
Moderate	23.6 ± 4.0	76	
Severe	26.0 ± 4.5	32	

The mean fasting blood glucose levels for mild, moderate, and severe acne were 87.2 mg/dL (SD = 8.9), 89.8 mg/dL (SD = 10.6), and 94.0 mg/dL (SD = 11.0), respectively. ANOVA analysis showed a significant difference in blood glucose levels across the acne severity groups (F(2, 177) = 6.23, p = 0.003).

The mean serum insulin levels for mild, moderate, and severe acne were 11.2 μIU/mL (SD = 3.6), 12.6 μIU/mL (SD = 4.7), and 15.8 μIU/mL (SD = 5.1), respectively. ANOVA analysis revealed a significant difference in serum insulin levels across the acne severity groups (F(2, 177) = 11.57, p < 0.001).

Table 3: Blood Glucose and Serum Insulin Levels Across Acne Severity Groups

Acne Severity	Mild	Moderate	Severe
Mean Fasting Blood Glucose (mg/dL)	87.2 ± 8.9	89.8 ± 10.6	94.0 ± 11.0
Mean Serum Insulin (μIU/mL)	11.2 ± 3.6	12.6 ± 4.7	15.8 ± 5.1
p-value (Glucose)	0.003		
p-value (Insulin)	<0.001		

A favourable link was found using Pearson correlation analysis between BMI and blood glucose levels (r = 0.27, p < 0.001) and serum insulin levels (r = 0.42, p < 0.001). Additionally, there was a favourable association (r = 0.34, p < 0.001) between blood glucose levels and serum insulin levels.

Table 4: Correlation Matrix

Variable	BMI	Blood Glucose	Serum Insulin
BMI	1	0.27	0.42
Blood Glucose	0.27	1	0.34
Serum Insulin	0.42	0.34	1

Multiple linear regression analysis was conducted to assess the predictors of acne severity. BMI, blood glucose, and serum insulin levels were included as independent variables. The model was statistically significant (F(3, 176) = 22.67, p < 0.001) and explained 28.1% of the variance in acne severity (R² = 0.281).

Table 5: Multiple Linear Regression Analysis Predicting Acne Severity

Predictor	B	SE	β	t	p-value
BMI	0.321	0.073	0.332	4.397	<0.001
Blood Glucose	0.087	0.028	0.201	3.096	0.002
Serum Insulin	0.147	0.036	0.294	4.083	<0.001

Discussion

The body mass index (BMI), blood sugar, and serum insulin levels in teenage acne sufferers were assessed in this study. The study involved 180 participants in all, ages 12 to 18. The results showed a strong correlation between more severe

acne and higher serum insulin levels, fasting blood glucose, and body mass index.

With a mean age of 15.6 years, the study sample comprised nearly equal numbers of male and female individuals. The average serum insulin level was 12.5 μIU/mL, the average fasting blood glucose level was 89.6 mg/dL, and the average

BMI was 23.4 kg/m². The participants' overall health state was comprehensively outlined by these baseline variables.

Groups for mild, moderate, and severe acne were created from the participants. According to the findings, people with severe acne had a mean BMI that was noticeably higher than people with mild to moderate acne. This implies that a higher body mass index (BMI) could be associated with more severe acne, possibly as a result of fat tissue's impact on hormone levels and inflammatory mechanisms.

Significant variations were observed in serum insulin levels and fasting blood glucose levels across the groups with varying degrees of acne severity. Compared to individuals with milder forms of acne, those with severe acne had higher mean blood glucose and serum insulin levels. This suggests that the pathophysiology of acne may involve insulin resistance and altered glucose metabolism.

The positive correlations between BMI and serum insulin levels, BMI and blood glucose levels, and serum insulin and blood glucose levels suggest a complex interplay between metabolic factors and acne severity. Higher BMI was associated with higher insulin and glucose levels, which could exacerbate acne by promoting hyperinsulinemia and androgen production.

Multiple linear regression analysis identified BMI, blood glucose, and serum insulin levels as significant predictors of acne severity. The model explained 28.1% of the variance in acne severity, indicating that these metabolic factors are important contributors to acne pathogenesis. The strong association between these variables underscores the need for a holistic approach in managing acne, considering both dermatological and metabolic aspects.

The study's findings highlight the significant associations between metabolic health and acne severity in adolescents. Higher BMI, blood glucose, and serum insulin levels were linked to more severe acne, suggesting that addressing metabolic dysfunctions could be beneficial in acne management. These results emphasize the importance of comprehensive health assessments in adolescents with acne and suggest potential therapeutic targets for improving both metabolic health and acne outcomes.

An investigation on serum irisin levels and insulin resistance (IR) in teenagers with acne vulgaris (AV) was conducted. There were 40 AV sufferers and 40 healthy controls in the trial. In patients with AV, serum irisin levels were considerably lower and had a negative correlation with IR. According to the study's findings, IR is more common in AV

patients, particularly in those with severe lesions, which may be related to lowered irisin levels in the serum [5].

In 184 subjects, a study assessed the relationship between AV, visceral adiposity index (VAI), and insulin resistance (IR). According to the study, there was no discernible difference in the HOMA index or VAI between the AV and control groups, indicating that visceral adipose tissue dysfunction and IR by themselves are not sufficient to cause acne [6].

Research was done on teenage girls who had PCOS, or polycystic ovarian syndrome, and AN, or acanthosis nigricans. There were notable variations between the AN and non-AN groups in terms of BMI, abdominal circumference, and insulin resistance. According to the study's findings, AN is a sign of obesity but not always a sign of underlying glucose intolerance or insulin resistance [7].

Serum galectin-3 levels and their correlation with IR were assessed in 60 AV patients and 20 control subjects. The results of the study showed that AV patients, especially those with severe lesions, had considerably higher levels of galectin-3 and HOMA-IR, suggesting that IR is more common in these patients. Elevated blood levels of galectin-3 have been associated with the intensity of AV [8].

A study looked at the relationship between acne severity and body mass index (BMI) and the serum levels of insulin-like growth factor-1 (IGF-1) in acne patients compared to controls. IGF-1's significance in the pathophysiology of acne vulgaris is supported by the study's finding that patients with acne had considerably higher serum IGF-1 levels, which positively linked with both the severity of acne and BMI [9].

Conclusion

The results of the study showed a strong correlation between teenage acne severity and BMI, blood sugar, and serum insulin levels. Individuals with more severe acne had higher BMIs, blood glucose levels, and serum insulin levels, which may indicate a connection between metabolic variables and the pathophysiology of acne. These results emphasize how crucial it is to control teenage acne while taking metabolic health into account.

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